

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№ 10

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Elektron nashr. 882 sahifa.

2025-yil, 19-oktyabr

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate

Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor

Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor

Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)

Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer

Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor

Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow))

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI YASHIL ENERGIYA: BARCHA UCHUN MUHIM MASALA.....	13
Muxiddin Kalonov	
MOLIYAVIY INNOVATSIYALAR: IQTISODIY MOHIYATI, QO‘LLANILISHI VA RIVOJLANISHI.....	19
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	
SAVDO KORXONALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA STATISTIK TAHLIL USULLARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI.....	24
Sabirova Oysuluv Shonazarovna	
KORXONANING MEBEL MAXSULOTLARI BOZORIDAGI O‘RNINI KENGAYTIRISH USULLARI	30
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INVESTITSIYA KO‘RSATKICHLARI TIZIMINING FUNKSIONAL JIHATI.....	35
Alabayev Sobitxon	
MAMLAKATIMIZDA MAHSULOTLARNING MUVOFIQLIGINI BAHOLASH AMALIYOTI.....	40
Zakirov Ansabxon Akaidinovich	
ПЕСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЁНЫХ ОБЛИГАЦИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	48
Саидахмедова Аида Мирзаевна	
KORXONALAR FAOLIYATIDA DEBITOR VA KREDITOR QARZDORLIKNI BOSHQARISH	55
Mirzayev Ozod Furkatovich	
AHOLI PUL DAROMADLARI VA HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISH KO‘RSATKICHLARI O‘RTASIDAGI EKONOMETRIK TAHLIL.....	59
Qodirov Farrux Ergash o‘g‘li	
BUDJET RESURSLARI SHAKLLANISHIDA HUDUDNING SOLIQ SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH VA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIK.....	64
Yuldashev Adhamjon Axadjonovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHI TUSHUNCHASIGA NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	69
Muydinov Xusniddin Nuriddin o‘g‘li	
МЕТОДИКА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫМИ ПОТОКАМИ В СИСТЕМЕ УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКОГО УЧЕТА	73
Минутдинова Лилия Тагировна, Машарипов Озод Алимович	
ГАРМОНИЗАЦИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С МСФО	78
Абдужалилова Дилноз Абдусаттаровна	
RAQAMLI TECHNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA SMART TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING DOLZARBLIGI	84
Sobirjonov Muxiddin Toxirjon o‘g‘li	
TO‘LOVGA QOBILIYATSIZLIK HOLATIDAGI KORXONALARDA TUGATISH BALANSINI TUZISH.....	90
Nabiyev Gofurjon Nosirjon o‘g‘li	
O‘ZBEKISTON SANOATINING “YASHIL” IQTISODIYOTGA O‘TAYOTGANLIGI: IMKONIYATLAR VA CHEKLOVLAR	96
Habibullayev Oybek Asliddin o‘g‘li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT KONTSEPTSIYASINING EVOLYUTSIYASI VA ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	102
Allayarov Suxrob Rustamovich	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA TO‘G‘RIDAN-TO‘G‘RI CHET EL INVESTITSIYALARINING MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI ROLI	107
Raxmatov Adxam Itolmasovich, Boynazarova Matluba Xatamovna	

HUDUDIY IJTIMOY TENGLIK VA KAMBAG'ALLIKNI YUMSHATISHDA MEHNAT RESURSLARI OMILLARI.....	114
Durumov Temur G'olibovich	
TRANSPORT TARMOG'I VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNING ASOSIY TARMOQLARI O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIKNI MODELASHTIRISH (SURXANDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	121
Turayev Baxtiyor Ergashevich, Aymatov Sirojiddin To'raqul o'g'li	
РОЛЬ ЭНЕРГЕТИКИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РОСТА ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	134
Нигматуллаева Гулчехра Нуруллаевна	
O'ZBEKISTONDA OLIY TA'LIM BOZORINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENTSIYALARI VA UNDA SIFAT MENEJMENTINING ROLI.....	139
Yuldashev Iskandar Bahromovich	
YER QA'RIDAN FOYDALANUVCHILARGA SOLIQ SOLISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	145
Zoxidov Ismatjon Yunusjon o'g'li	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA TURIZM INDUSTRIYASIDA INNOVATSION BIZNES-MODELLAR.....	151
Shaxinabonu Choriyeva	
AVTOTRANSPORT – EKSPEDITSIYA XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA MARKETING KONTSEPSIYASI.....	157
Ergasheva Mukhabbat Abdusamatovna	
“YASHIL” ENERGIYA ISHLAB CHIQRUVCHI KICHIK TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINI SOLIQQA TORTISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	163
Toshemirov To'liqin Toirjonovich	
DAVLAT IQTISODIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SIYOSIY INSTITUTLARNING ROLI VA UNI KUCHAYTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	166
O. Nurmuradov	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RAQAMLI BANK TEXNOLOGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ASOSLARI	171
Meyliqulov Shaxboz Xolmamat o'g'li	
СВЯЗНОСТЬ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТРАТЕГИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ.....	176
Ташматов Гайрат Ровшанович, Содиков Авазбек Мадаминович	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI TURIZM SOHASINI RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA RIVOJLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	183
Zarikeyeva Miyasar Maratovna	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYASI.....	187
Saidrahmatova Zuhraxon Saidazim qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON KONCHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA INVESTITSION JARAYONLARNI BOSHQARISH VA INNOVATSION XAVFLARNI KAMAYTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI	192
Kurbanova Mehriniso Nematjanovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA QULAY INVESTITSIYA MUHITINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MUAMMOLARI.....	196
Xuramov Zafar Rajabaliyevich	
PAHTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARIDA XOMASHYO TA'MINOTI BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING XORIJ DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	201
Zakirov Abduazim Abdurashidovich	
НОВЫЙ ЭТАП ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ РЫНОЧНЫХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ В ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	206
Махкамов Ибраим	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SUG'URTA BOZORINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENTSIYALARI.....	213
Xushmuradov Oman, Ismoilov Sherzod Ismoil o'g'li	
GLOBALIZATSIYA SHAROITIDA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT NAZARIYASI.....	217
Mo'yidinov Xurshidbek Abdullayevich	
DORIVOR O'SIMLIKLARNI QAYTA ISHLASHNING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI	221
Usmonov Mirg'ulom Xoshim o'g'li	

BARQAROR IQTISODIY O‘SISHGA YERISHISHDA SUN’IY INTELLEKT TIZIMLARINI QO‘LLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILASHTIRISH (XORIJIY DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI MISOLIDA)	227
Nasrulloev Hayotjon Xabibulloevich	
НЕЙРОИНТУИТИВНЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ И ЕГО РОЛЬ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ РИСКАМИ В БИЗНЕСЕ.....	233
Ягудин Дмитрий Рустамович	
RESURLARNI SOLIQQA TORTISH AMALIYOTINING XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI VA ULARNING MILLIY SOLIQQA TIZIMIDA QO‘LLASH MASALALARI	240
Nasimdjanoov Yunusjon Zoxidovich	
O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA KICHIK TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI UCHUN QO‘LLANILAYOTGAN SOLIQQA TORTISH MEKANIZMLARI	246
Akbarov Akramjon Ibragimzhonovich	
TO‘QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA “YASHIL” MARKETINGNI JORIY ETISHNING DOLZARB JIHATLARI	250
Bazarova Fayyoza Tuxtamurodovna	
INSON KAPITALI VA IQTISODIYOTNING RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYASI.....	255
Muzaffar Raximov	
UY-JOY KOMMUNAL XO‘JALIGINI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	259
Odamboyev Oybek Ravshanbek o‘g‘li	
INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS’ APPROACHES TO ATTRACTING INVESTMENT IN HUMAN CAPITAL	268
Akhmadaliyeva Nikholakhon	
RAQAMLI PLATFORMALAR ORQALI KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘LLARI.....	273
Vohobov Hikmatillo Ma‘mirjon o‘g‘li	
ФОРСАЙТ И ЭКОНОМИЧНЫЕ ИННОВАЦИИ КАК ДРАЙВЕРЫ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ТОРГОВЛИ САМАРКАНДА	280
Tohirova Gullola Mirkamolovna	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI BOSHQARISHDA KASB-HUNAR TA‘LIMI BITIRUVCHILARINING O‘RNI	287
Toshpulatov Sherzod Xaydarkulovich	
DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ECOTOURISM: INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR ADVANCING GREEN TOURISM.....	292
Barno Erkayeva	
AGROTURIZM SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	296
Baymuradova Iroda Shermamatovna, Mardonova Zarifa Numonjonovna	
DAVLAT BUDJET NAZORATI TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘NALISHLARI	301
B.Sh.Mirzayev	
YOSHLAR BANDLIGIDA KO‘NIKMALAR NOMUTANOSIBLIGI MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI.....	307
Rahmatxo‘jayev Axrorxo‘ja Akmal o‘g‘li	
TO‘QIMACHILIK MAHSULOTLARINING EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI TAHLIL QILISH VA RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARINI BAHOLASH.....	311
Oqboyev Alisher Rasuljanovich	
РЕИНЖИНИРИНГ БИЗНЕС-ПРОЦЕССОВ И ИХ РОЛЬ В РАЗВИТИИ БАНКОВСКОГО БИЗНЕСА.....	317
Рахимходжаева Нодира Саидахраловна	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGI TA‘MINOT ZANJIRI JARAYONLARINING HOZIRGI HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH.....	323
Ermonov Farrux	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI SHAKILLANTIRISH JARAYONIDA MOLIVAVIY NAZORATNI INNOVATSION TA‘LIM YO‘NALISHLARINI YO‘LGA QO‘YISH ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO‘LLARI.....	329
Turg‘unov Bahtiyor Nuriddinovich	

MARKAZIY OSIYODA SUV RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISH VA HAMKORLIKNING DOLZARB MASALALARI	334
Amanbaev Amanali Orazbaevich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA YANGI TURDAGI LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINING USLUBIY ASOSLARI.....	338
Z. Teshayev	
O'ZBEKISTON AXBOROT-KOMMUNIKATSIYA XIZMATLARI SOHASINING AMALDAGI HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH.....	343
Suyunov Asror Baxtiyorovich	
KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVDA LEADERSHIP 4.0 TAMOYILLARINI JORIY ETISH SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	349
Ismailov Allayor Rashidovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA AHOLI BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASH MASALALARI.....	355
Yusupov Farxod Adamboyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI O'RNI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNI USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	359
Abdullaeva Nilufar Javdat qizi	
MINTAQADA SANOAT KORXONALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING SOLISHTIRMA EKONOMETRIK MODELLARI (SURXONDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	363
Saatmurotov Shohrux Zafar o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORI: RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI VA ISTIQBOLLI IMKONIYATLAR	369
Abdurazaqov Jasur Abdunasimovich	
RAQAMLI PLATFORMALAR YORDAMIDA NORASMIY VA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI QISQARTIRISHNING QO'SHIMCHA IMKONIYATLARI TO'G'RSIDA.....	374
Nasrullayev Hikmatullo Habibulloyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH MAQSADIDA "XIZMATLAR IPOTEKASI" MOLIYAVIY INSTRUMENTLARINI AMALIYOTGA JORIY QILISH MASALALARI	379
Uskenbayeva Dilnoza Boxodir qizi	
ЭКОНОМИКО-СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ КАПЕЛЬНОГО ОРОШЕНИЯ ПРИ ВОЗДЕЛЫВАНИИ ЛУКА В ДЖИЗАКСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	384
Суюнов Шохзодбек Мурод угли	
XORIJY DAVLATLAR SANOAT IQTISODIYOTIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH TAJRIBASI (YAPONIYA, KOREYA VA GERMANIYA MISOLIDA)	389
Mansurova Sayyora Baxtiyor Kizi	
KORXONALARDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH XARAJATLARI HISOBGA OLIHDA XORIY TAJRIBASINI QO'LLASH	395
Raxmatov Baxriddin Baxtiyor o'g'li	
PECULIARITIES OF THE IRRIGATION WATER DELIVERY PAYMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	399
Muminov Sherzod Kholmiraevich	
DIGITALIZATION OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS FOR EXPORT	404
Azimov R.B.	
AHOLI JON BOSHIGA UMUMIY DAROMADLAR HAJMINI TREND MODELLAR ASOSIDA PROGNOZLASH	409
Xolto'rayev Islom Ilhomovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA YANGI BANDLIK SHAKLLARI	416
Sayipov Begzod Rahimovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING YANGI DAVR SHAROITIDA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASH USULLARI VA INDIKATORLARI	422
Sadikov Iskandar Gayratovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI AKTIVLARINING SAMARADORLIGINI IQTISODIY-STATISTIK TAHLILI	427
Ibrohimov Davronbek Muhammadi o'g'li	

MAHALLIY BUDJET SOLIQLI DAROMADLARI BAZASI BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SOLIQLAR TA'SIRCHANLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	433
<i>Isoqov Zafarjon Zokirjonovich</i>	
TOSHKENT SHAHRIDAGI YIRIK SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILARNING SOLIQ QARZDORLIGI TAHLILI	438
<i>Soipov Boburmirzo Nosirjon o'g'li</i>	
РОЛЬ ЖИЛИЩНОЙ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ В СИСТЕМЕ КОМПЛЕКСНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ТЕРРИТОРИЙ МЕЗОУРОВНЯ.....	446
<i>Далиев Ахтам Шарафудинович</i>	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INSON RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHDA XORIJ TAJRIBALARINING ZARURLIGI.....	454
<i>Abdullayev Dostonbek G'ofurjon o'g'li</i>	
TURISTIK KLASTERLARNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA ULARNING HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI	458
<i>Xaitov Oxunjon Nomoz o'g'li</i>	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA RESURS TA'MINOTI BOSHQARUVINING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYALARI VA MODELLARI.....	462
<i>Arziqulova Oybar chin Eshquvat qizi</i>	
XIZMATLAR SEKTORIDA RAQAMLI INNOVATSIYALAR VA MIJOZLAR EHTIYOJLARINI QONDIRISH MEKANIZMLARI	467
<i>Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich</i>	
СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ СУЩНОСТЬ ПОДГОТОВКИ КАДРОВ В РАЗВИТИИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА.....	472
<i>Базаров Бердымурад Улугмуродович, Атавуллаева Саида Джумабекмуродовна</i>	
TURIZM SOHASIDA KADRLAR SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISHNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMI.....	478
<i>Ho'jaqulov Bobur Rustam o'g'li</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA DAVLATNING RO'LI	483
<i>Nabiyeva Muxabbat Djabirxanovna</i>	
"HOW GREEN INVESETMENTS CAN EFFECT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES"	485
<i>Farangiz Ma'rufjonovna Pirmatova</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA UZOQ MUDDATLI RESURSLAR MANBALARI VA ULARNING HAJMINI OSHIRISHNING ZARURIYATI.....	493
<i>Abduraxmonov Akmal Nurmat o'g'li</i>	
GLOBAL BOSHQARUV VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHDA YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALARNING ROLI	498
<i>M.Sh. Tolipov</i>	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕХАНИЗМОВ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВОЙ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ	504
<i>Буранбаева Шоира Рустамовна</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA PIYOZ YETISHTIRISHDA TOMCHILATIB SUG'ORISHNI QO'LLASH ISTIQBOLLARI	508
<i>Suyunov Shohzodbek Murod o'g'li</i>	
YENGIL SANOAT KORXONALARINING RIVOJLANISHIGA BOSHQARUV MADANIYATIDAN FOYDALANISHNING TA'SIRI.....	513
<i>Aknazarova Zebiniso Bagdadovna</i>	
ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASH SHAROITIDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZM SAMARADORLIGINI ANIQLASH USULLARI	518
<i>Qurbaniyazov Shaxzodbek Karimovich</i>	
KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA JOYLASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY VA TASHKILIY ASOSLARI	524
<i>Salimov Burxon Abubakirovich</i>	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA UNDA ENERGIYADAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	530
<i>Berdiyeva Aziza G'anisher qizi</i>	

SIRKULAR IQTISODIYOTDAN KORXONA VA TADBIRKORLAR MANFAATLARI	535
Sodikov Zokir Rustamovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK SOHASIDA ME'YORIY-HUQUQIY BAZANI ISHLAB CHIQISH.....	541
Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Ubaydullayev Toxirjon Abdullajanovich	
MINTAQA OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARI CHAKANA SAVDOSIDA SHADOW WAREHOUSE MODELIGA ASOSLANGAN YETKAZIB BERISH TIZIMINI JORIY QILISH.....	548
Ibrayimova Dilnoza Abdisherpovna	
XIZMATLAR SAVDOSI SOHASIDA O'ZBEKISTONNING XALQARO HAMKORLIK IMKONIYATLARI	555
Qodirjonov A.M.	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATINI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANTIRISHDA RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH KONSEPSIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH USLUBIYOTI.....	559
Madraximova Gulasal Ro'zimboy qizi	
ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ ТРЕНДЫ СМАРТ-ТУРИЗМА И ИХ ПРИМЕНИМОСТЬ К КУЛЬТУРНОМУ НАСЛЕДИЮ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	564
Салихбаев Нурсултон Равшанович	
IJTIMOIIY NIHOYA TIZIMI VA IJTIMOIIY TIBBIY XIZMATLAR O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIGINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	572
Shanazarov Farrux Shodiyorovich	
ТЕХНИКО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЕ ОБОСНОВАНИЕ РАЗРАБОТКИ МОБИЛЬНОГО ПРИЛОЖЕНИЯ JOB VARAKA ДЛЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	577
Еримбетова Улбосын Маратовна	
TASHQI SAVDO VA INVESTITSIYALAR TAHLILI HAMDA ULARNING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKKA TA'SIRI.....	582
Jalolov Bekzod Sherzod o'g'li	
“O'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESLAR UCHUN SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA MOLIYAVIY KO'RSATKICHLARNI TAHLIL QILISH VA RAQAMLI YECHIMLAR TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH”	586
Azamatjon Mardayev Abdusamat o'g'li	
FARMATSEVIKA MAHSULOTLARI ISHLAB CHIQARUVCHI KORXONALARDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ME'YORIY-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI.....	591
Xudaynazarova Dilnoza Gafurovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INNOVASION TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA KADRLAR TAYYORLASH MENEJMENTINING AMAL QILISH USULLARI VA TURLARI	596
Ergashev To'liqin Shokirovich	
HUDUDIIY IQTISODIYOTNI RAQAMLI TEKNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	602
Ibragimov Baxrom Baxodirovich	
ISLOMIY MOLIYA INSTRUMENTLARINI JORIY ETISH ORQALI O'ZBEKISTONDA MOLIYA BOZORINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI.....	606
Xodjayev Aziz Shovkatovich	
MAHALLIY HOKIMIYAT QAROR QABUL QILISH JARAYONLARIDA DINAMIK OMILLAR VA ULARNING INTEGRATSIYASI	611
Axmedov Farxod Raxmonjonovich	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLAR AUDITINI TASHKIL ETISH VA TAHLIL QILISH METODLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	617
Rizakulov Abdurauf Abdimutalibovich	
ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ПРИВЛЕКАТЕЛЬНОСТИ ТУРИЗМА ЧЕРЕЗ КРЕАТИВНУЮ ИНДУСТРИЮ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН.....	623
Хошимова Камилла Навфал қизи	
IMITATION MODELDA AXBOROT NORAVSHANLIGI SABABLI YUZAGA KELADIGAN IQTISODIY SAMARASIZLIK TAHLILI.....	633
Qodirov Zohidjon Eralievich	

JISMONIY SHAXSLAR TOMONIDAN KREDITLARDAN FOYDALANISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	637
Turdiyeva Kumush Erkinovna	
SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH XIZMATLARI SOHASIDA SIFATNI BAHOLASH KO'RSATKICHLARI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIK O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIK.....	641
Usmanova Nasiba Akbarjonovna, Eshbekova Xayriniso Baxtiyorovna	
SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILAR FAOLIYATINING SEGMENTATSIYASIGA ASOSLANIB SOLIQ XAVFLARINI ANIQLASH VA BAHOLASHNING AMALIY YONDOSHUVI	648
Elbaeva M.R.	
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI.....	653
Hamroyev G'ayratjon Sultonovich	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI SIFAT MENEJMENTI TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA TASHKIL ETISHNING XORIJ MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI	657
Achilov Ilmurad	
MINTAQALAR INVESTITSION SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY VA METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	663
Qobilov Anvar Eshpo'lotovich	
KORXONALARNING YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYASINI ISHLAB CHIQISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	669
Sapayev Axmed Durdibayevich	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHDA KO'P MEZONLI TAHLIL USULLARINI QO'LLASH.....	674
Muxammadaliyev Mirzohidjon Muxammadali o'g'li	
BOJXONA HUDUDIDA QAYTA ISHLASH BOJXONA REJIMINING AMALDAGI HOLATI TAHLILI	681
Abdullayev Shaxzodbek	
ENSURING SUSTAINABLE REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH INTEGRATION OF RECREATION AND ECOTOURISM RESOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN	686
Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna	
MAKROIQTISODIYOTDA ISTE'MOL VA JAMG'ARISH FUNSIYALARI VA ULARNING O'ZBEKISTONDA O'ZGARISHI TENDENSIYALARI	691
Rustamov Narzillo Istamovich	
CHAKANA SAVDONI BOSHQARISHDA "BIG MIDDLE" NAZARIYASIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	697
Yaqubov Azizbek G'anibekovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA HUNARMANDCHILIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PROGNOZ VARIANTLARI.....	701
Ermetov Amirbek Ismailovich	
FISKAL NOMARKAZLASHTIRISH BO'YICHA XITOIY TAJRIBASI.....	708
Lokayev Bekzod Sherkobilovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI BOSHQARUV TIZIMLARI: IMKONIYATLAR VA CHEKLOVLAR.....	712
Ismatullayeva Munixon Bori qizi	
EKOLOGIYA VA ATROF MUHITNI MUHOFAZA QILISH SOHASIDA DASTURIY BUDJETLASHTIRISH BO'YICHA XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	717
Dilshod Pulatov, Dildora Mirzaeva, Gulzora Qahharova	
TIKUV-TRIKOTAJ SANOATIDA MEHNAT UNUMDORLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI VA BOSHQARUV STRATEGIYALARI.....	725
Mardiyev Bunyod Sirojiddin o'g'li	
BURNOUTNING OLDINI OLIH: XODIMLAR SALOMATLIGI STRATEGIYASI.....	731
Ergasheva E'zoza Dilshod qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KORXONALARNING TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI.....	736
Pulatova Moxira Baxtiyorovna	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARIDA XARAJATLARNI BOSHQARISH VA HISOBGA OLIHNING INNOVATSION USULLARI: MENEJMENT VA BUXGALTERIYANING O'ZARO INTEGRATSIYASI.....	742
Mamadiyarov Dilshad Uralovich, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o'g'li	

RIVOJLANGAN MAMLAKATLARDA AHOLI DAROMADLARINI OSHIRISH MEKANIZMLARI	748
Uzoqov Suhrobjon Do'smat o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIMNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH MODELLARI	754
Talapova Nargiza Baxriddinovna	
ВОЗОБНОВЛЕНИЕ ДОБЫЧИ ПРИРОДНОГО ГАЗА ИЗ ТРЁХ СКВАЖИН УЧАСТКА ХОДЖАСАЯТ ГКМ ДЕНГИЗКУЛЬ	758
Набиев Шахзод Темурович, Иргашбаев Шохрух Фаррух угли, Маннафов Улугбек Умар угли	
MADANIY TURIZM INDUSTRIYASINING RIVOJLANISH IMKONIYATLARI VA O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	764
Toxirov Dilyor Davlatovich	
MOLIYAVIY AUTSORSING NAZARIYALARI VA UNING RIVOJLANISH BOSQICHLARI	768
Babadjanov Umidbek Kamildjanovich	
TURIZM – TARIXIY XOTIRA VA ZAMONAVIY XIZMATLAR UYG'UNLIGI IFODASI	773
Janzakov Bekzot Kulmamat o'g'li	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINING MOHIYATI VA BAHOLASH MEZONLARI	777
Abdikarimova Zilola Baxramovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARI AKTIVLARINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	784
Ro'ziyeva Shaxlo Salimboyevna	
AXBOROT TIZIMLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA TEXNIK XIZMAT KO'RSATISHNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH	788
Samiyeva Maftuna Faxriddin qizi	
TIJORAT BANKLARI AKTIVLARI DAROMADLILIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	791
Sanayev Javoxir Shovkat o'g'li	
FISCAL, MONETARY, AND CUSTOMS-TARIFF POLICIES IN ENSURING NATIONAL ECONOMIC STABILITY: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	796
Maxmudov S.T.	
ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ И РАЗВИТИЯ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИХ КЛАСТЕРОВ	801
Юсупова Н.Т.	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY O'SISHIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI ASOSIY FAKTORLAR TAHLILI	807
Rahimova Mushtariybegim Muxammadg'olib qizi	
DEMOGRAFIK O'ZGARISHLAR VA ULARNING IJTIMOY-IQTISODIY OQIBATLARI.....	812
Abdumalikova G.F.	
MINTAQAVIY INVESTITSIYA SIYOSATINI SAMARALI BOSHQARISHNING IQTISODIY VA INSTITUTSION ASOSLARI	821
Kenjayev Ikrom Ergashboyevich	
RAQAMLI AVIATSIYA EKOTIZIMI: AI/ML, DIGITAL TWIN VA BLOKCHEYN INTEGRATSIYASI	828
Azimova Moxinur Nozimovna	
XALQARO MOLIYA BOZORLARIDA INVESTITSIYA RISKLARINI BOSHQARISHNING ZAMONAVIY MEKANIZMLARI	834
G'afurov Sherzod Abduvaxob o'g'li	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATINING REKREATSIYA RESURLARI VA DAVOLASH-SOG'LOMLASHTIRISH TURIZMI SALOHIYATI	839
Murtazayeva Gulrux Isabek qizi	
MINTAQALAR TURISTIK-REKREATSION IMKONIYATLARINI BAHOLASHDA ZAMONAVIY GIS USULLARINI QO'LLASH (SARIOSIYO TUMANI MISOLIDA)	845
Safarov Manuchexr Axtam o'g'li	
XITOIY TAJRIBASI ASOSIDA INVESTITSIYA MUHITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	852
Tirkashev Farruxjon Xolyigitovich	
TURIZM FAOLIYATINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISHGA OID NAZARIY BILIMLARNING SHAKLLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI	857
Maxmudova Aziza Pirmamatovna	

TIJORAT BANKLARI RESURS BAZASI MUSTAHKAMLIGINI BAHOLOVCHI KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMI	863
Raxmanov Iloxom Xurramovich	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	871
Maxsudov Sherzod Solijonovich	
FISCAL, MONETARY, AND CUSTOMS-TARIFF POLICIES IN ENSURING NATIONAL ECONOMIC STABILITY: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	877
Mahmudov Sarvar	

FISCAL, MONETARY, AND CUSTOMS-TARIFF POLICIES IN ENSURING NATIONAL ECONOMIC STABILITY: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN

Mahmudov Sarvar

Academy of Public Policy and Administration
under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-8241-2879>

Abstract. This study investigates the effectiveness of Uzbekistan's fiscal, monetary, and customs-tariff policies in sustaining national economic stability amid structural transformation and global uncertainty. Using macroeconomic data from

2020-2024, the research analyzes changes in tax revenues, budget deficits, inflation, and external trade dynamics. Descriptive and comparative methods were applied to evaluate the outcomes of tax reforms, monetary interventions, and tariff liberalization measures. The results show that fiscal reforms -particularly tax base expansion and rate optimization- improved budget revenues, while targeted monetary policy helped reduce inflation from

16% in 2018 to about 10% by 2024. Additionally, customs-tariff adjustments during the 2020-2024 period stabilized consumer prices and supported food security. The findings suggest that Uzbekistan's integrated fiscal-monetary approach has strengthened macroeconomic resilience, although challenges remain in balancing social spending, external debt, and exchange rate stability.

Key words: fiscal policy, monetary policy, customs tariffs, economic stability, Uzbekistan, inflation control, tax reform.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot tizimli o'zgarishlar va global noaniqlik sharoitida milliy iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashda O'zbekistonning fiskal, pul-kredit va bojxona-tarif siyosatining samaradorligini o'rganadi. dan makroiqtisodiy ma'lumotlardan foydalanish.

2020-2024-yillarda tadqiqot soliq tushumlari, budget taqchilligi, inflyatsiya va tashqi savdo dinamikasidagi o'zgarishlarni tahlil qiladi. Soliq islohotlari, pul-kredit intervensiyalari va tariflarni liberallashtirish chora-tadbirlari natijalarini baholashda tavsiflovchi va qiyosiy usullar qo'llanildi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, fiskal islohotlar, xususan, soliq bazasini kengaytirish va stavkalarni optimallashtirish budget daromadlarini yaxshilagan bo'lsa, maqsadli pul-kredit siyosati inflyatsiya darajasini pasaytirishga yordam berdi.

2018-yilda 16 foizni, 2024-yilga kelib qariyb 10 foizni tashkil etadi. Bundan tashqari, 2020-2024-yillarda bojxona tariflarini o'zgartirish iste'mol narxlarini barqarorlashtirdi va oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini qo'llab-quvvatladi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, O'zbekistonning integratsiyalashgan fiskal-monetar yondashuvi makroiqtisodiy barqarorlikni mustahkamladi, garchi ijtimoiy xarajatlar, tashqi qarz va valyuta kursi barqarorligini muvozanatlashda muammolar saqlanib qolmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: fiskal siyosat, pul-kredit siyosati, bojxona tariflari, iqtisodiy barqarorlik, O'zbekiston, inflyatsiyani nazorat qilish, soliq islohoti.

Аннотация. В настоящем исследовании рассматривается эффективность фискальной, денежно-кредитной и таможенно-тарифной политики Узбекистана в поддержании национальной экономической стабильности в условиях структурной трансформации и глобальной неопределенности. Используя макроэкономические данные за 2020–2024 годы, исследование анализирует изменения в налоговых поступлениях, дефиците бюджета, инфляции и динамике внешней торговли. Для оценки результатов налоговых реформ, денежно-кредитных интервенций и мер по либерализации тарифов были применены описательные и сравнительные методы. Результаты показывают, что фискальные реформы, в частности расширение налоговой базы и оптимизация ставок, улучшили доходы бюджета, а целевая денежно-кредитная политика способствовала снижению инфляции с 16% в 2018 году до примерно 10% к 2024 году. Кроме того, корректировка таможенно-тарифных ставок в период 2020–2024 годов стабилизировала потребительские цены и способствовала продовольственной безопасности. Результаты свидетельствуют о том, что комплексный фискально-денежный подход Узбекистана укрепил макроэкономическую устойчивость, хотя сохраняются проблемы с балансировкой социальных расходов, внешнего долга и стабильности обменного курса.

Ключевые слова: фискальная политика, денежно-кредитная политика, таможенные тарифы, экономическая стабильность, Узбекистан, контроль за инфляцией, налоговая реформа.

1. INTRODUCTION

Economic stability represents the cornerstone of sustainable national development, particularly in emerging economies navigating structural reforms and global economic shocks. In Uzbekistan, the transition toward a market-based economy has required an active state role in designing and implementing fiscal, monetary, and trade policies that ensure growth while mitigating inflationary and external risks [1,2]. In this context, macroeconomic management serves multiple, interlocking objectives: safeguarding price stability, preserving debt sustainability, smoothing cyclical fluctuations, and building buffers against external terms-of-trade and supply-chain shocks. The credibility of these policies is equally important, as well-anchored expectations lower risk premia, reduce dollarization incentives, and strengthen private investment responses.

Fiscal policy reforms since 2017 have targeted the expansion of the tax base, modernization of tax administration, and equitable distribution of tax burdens [3]. These efforts have been reinforced by a new Tax Code (effective 2020), the introduction of digital reporting systems, and the gradual reduction of key tax rates such as value-added tax (VAT) from 20% to 12% by 2023 [4]. Such measures were aimed at improving business competitiveness and stimulating domestic demand. Beyond rate changes, the reform agenda has emphasized simplification of procedures, broadening of the formal sector, and the adoption of program and medium-term budgeting to enhance allocative efficiency. Together, these shifts reflect a move from ad hoc, short-term adjustments toward a rules- and results-oriented fiscal framework that links resources to outcomes.

Monetary policy has complemented fiscal adjustments by maintaining price stability, managing inflation expectations, and promoting the credibility of the national currency, the Uzbek so'm. Since the adoption of inflation targeting in 2019, the Central Bank of Uzbekistan has pursued a strict interest rate policy to achieve a medium-term inflation goal of 5% [5]. Consistent communication, improved forecasting, and strengthened policy transmission-through more market-based interest rates and deepening of the domestic securities market-have supported the disinflation process. These steps are consequential in a small open economy where exchange-rate dynamics, imported inflation, and commodity-price volatility can quickly pass through to domestic prices.

Simultaneously, customs-tariff liberalization has played a significant role in supporting macroeconomic stability. By reducing import duties on essential goods and encouraging regional trade integration, Uzbekistan has improved supply-side efficiency and consumer welfare [6,7]. Lower barriers for critical inputs and food staples help stabilize production costs and headline inflation during external shocks, while trade facilitation and harmonization of procedures reduce non-tariff frictions. Over the medium term, such measures can foster competitiveness by integrating domestic firms into regional value chains and expanding market access.

Against this backdrop, a coordinated policy mix-linking prudent fiscal management, credible monetary policy, and open, efficient trade regimes -becomes central to sustaining growth and protecting living standards. Yet important questions remain regarding the relative contributions of each policy lever, their interactions over the business cycle, and the distributional implications of reforms across firms and households. There is also a need to assess whether recent institutional changes-digital tax administration, medium-term budgeting, and tariff rationalization-have translated into measurable gains in revenue mobilization, inflation control, and external stability.

The objective of this research is to analyze the empirical performance of Uzbekistan's fiscal, monetary, and customs-tariff policies between 2020 and 2024, assessing their combined effects on economic stability indicators such as GDP growth, inflation, budget balance, and employment. By integrating descriptive and comparative evidence across these three policy domains, the study seeks to (i) document key trends during a period of heightened uncertainty, (ii) identify complementarities and trade-offs within the policy mix, and (iii) derive practical implications for calibrating reforms that support resilient, inclusive growth in the years ahead.

2. METHODS

2.1. Data Sources

This research is based on official data from the Ministry of Economy and Finance, the Central Bank of Uzbekistan, and the State Statistics Committee, covering 2020-2024. Complementary information was drawn from presidential decrees (PF-21, PF-39, PF-149) and reports from Mikrokreditbank related to credit support for entrepreneurship and employment.

2.2. Analytical Approach

The study employed descriptive and comparative statistical methods, including ratio analysis and growth dynamics. Budget and tax data were expressed as percentages of GDP, while inflation and exchange rate changes were analyzed using trend comparison.

The tax burden (B) was estimated using the formula:

$$B = \frac{T \times 100\%}{In}$$

where T denotes total tax payments during the fiscal year and In is total sales revenue.

2.3. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual model integrates fiscal, monetary, and customs-tariff instruments as interdependent levers of macroeconomic stability. The model assumes that fiscal efficiency influences aggregate demand, monetary policy manages inflation expectations, and tariff reforms affect supply-side competitiveness.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Fiscal Policy and Budget Dynamics

Table 1 presents the composition of Uzbekistan's state budget revenues as a share of GDP. Between 2020 and 2024, total budget revenues averaged 22% of GDP, with minor fluctuations due to pandemic-related spending and tax adjustments [8].

Indicator	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Total revenue (% of GDP)	22	22.3	22.6	21.7	21.6
Direct taxes	7.5	8	7.2	6.9	7
Indirect taxes	7.7	7.6	8	7.8	7.7

Budget deficits varied from 2.5% of GDP in 2018 to 5.5% in 2023, reflecting counter-cyclical measures during COVID-19 and subsequent global disruptions. Fiscal consolidation efforts in 2024 reduced the deficit to 3.2% of GDP.

3.2. Tax Reforms and Administrative Efficiency

Tax policy reforms expanded revenue potential while improving equity. Despite VAT reductions, revenues from indirect taxes rose 1.9 times between 2020 and 2024, due to enhanced tax administration and reduced evasion. Direct taxes increased 2.0 times, driven by improved corporate profit taxation and formalization of economic activity.

Case studies of private firms show that the average tax burden (B) rose from 0.6 in 2020 to 4.3 in 2024, suggesting improved compliance but also indicating persistent fiscal pressure on enterprises [9].

3.3. Monetary Policy and Inflation Trends

Inflation peaked at 20.5% in 2018 following currency liberalization but steadily declined thereafter. As shown in Figure 1, inflation dropped to 10% by 2023, marking the lowest level in five years [10].

The Central Bank maintained a tight monetary stance, holding the base rate at 13.5% in 2024 to anchor inflation expectations, which remained around 10-12%. Exchange rate depreciation slowed to 3.7% in 2024, supported by international reserves totaling USD 41.2 billion, equivalent to 12 months of imports [11].

3.4. Financial Resource Utilization through State Programs

Government-backed financial programs through Mikrokreditbank have played a critical role in supporting employment and entrepreneurship. Between 2021 and 2024, more than 311,000 concessional loans worth 6,083.8 billion soums were issued, creating over 315,000 new jobs [12].

3.5. Customs-Tariff Policy and External Stability

Customs reforms reduced import duties on essential goods, stabilizing domestic prices. The 2022-2024 zero-duty regime on food items like flour, oil, and meat mitigated inflationary shocks from global food price surges. Consequently, food inflation was contained below 12%, compared to regional averages exceeding 20% [13].

Liberalized trade policies, including improved regional integration and WTO accession negotiations, have expanded foreign trade volume and enhanced market competitiveness.

4. DISCUSSION

The findings confirm that Uzbekistan's coordinated fiscal, monetary, and trade policies have collectively reinforced economic stability. Fiscal modernization improved tax collection efficiency and business incentives, while monetary restraint ensured disinflation without halting growth. The alignment of these policies has helped maintain macroeconomic balance amid both domestic structural reforms and global disruptions, including the lingering effects of the COVID-19 pandemic and commodity market volatility. Importantly, the period from 2020 to 2024 demonstrates that a synchronized policy mix—where fiscal expansion is counterbalanced by prudent monetary management and open trade policy—can mitigate external shocks and sustain momentum toward long-term development goals.

Fiscal policy has played a dual role, acting as both a stabilizer and a developmental tool. On one hand, targeted spending programs and concessional credit schemes supported aggregate demand and employment, cushioning the economy against cyclical downturns. On the other, reforms to tax policy and administration enhanced efficiency, broadened the tax base, and improved compliance through digitalization and automation. Nevertheless, the evidence suggests a growing need to balance fiscal consolidation with growth-friendly investment in infrastructure, innovation, and human capital. While tax revenues have increased substantially, the rising burden on certain enterprises—especially small and medium-sized firms—may discourage reinvestment and productivity gains, calling for a more nuanced, incentive-based approach to corporate taxation.

Monetary policy has contributed effectively to price stabilization, yet challenges persist in anchoring expectations at the target level. Persistent inflation expectations above the medium-term goal of 5% suggest limited transmission of monetary policy through the credit and exchange rate channels. This is partly due to structural rigidities in financial intermediation, shallow capital markets, and a relatively high level of dollarization in the economy. To strengthen policy transmission, the Central Bank may consider expanding open-market operations, enhancing communication strategies, and improving coordination with fiscal authorities to ensure that short-term budgetary measures do not undermine monetary targets. The gradual transition to inflation targeting remains a complex process requiring deep institutional credibility, accurate forecasting models, and consistent public communication.

Trade and customs-tariff reforms have also emerged as a stabilizing component of Uzbekistan's macroeconomic framework. By lowering tariffs on essential imports and simplifying customs procedures, the government successfully moderated imported inflation and strengthened food security during periods of global price spikes. In addition to mitigating supply-side constraints, trade liberalization fosters competition, innovation, and productivity growth. However, maintaining external stability requires careful calibration of tariff policy to prevent excessive import dependence and ensure sufficient domestic value addition. In the medium term, complementing tariff reforms with export diversification strategies and logistics modernization will be essential for long-run external sustainability.

Despite these achievements, several systemic vulnerabilities remain.

The rising tax burden on some enterprises may limit private investment and hinder SME growth, suggesting the need for differentiated tax treatment and expanded fiscal incentives for innovation and employment.

Persistent inflation expectations above target levels indicate that monetary policy transmission remains incomplete, warranting improved coordination between fiscal and financial sector reforms.

The budget deficit's sensitivity to external borrowing and commodity prices highlights the importance of strengthening fiscal buffers and developing domestic debt markets to reduce exposure to global fluctuations.

The integration of green and digital fiscal mechanisms could further enhance policy effectiveness, echoing recommendations by international experts such as Tanzi and Zee [14]. Green budgeting and climate-related expenditure tagging would align fiscal priorities with environmental sustainability, while digital public finance systems could improve efficiency, transparency, and accountability in budget execution. Moreover, real-time fiscal data analytics would enable policymakers to evaluate spending effectiveness and fine-tune interventions based on performance outcomes rather than ex post assessments. Continuous monitoring of fiscal multipliers and the cost-effectiveness of tax incentives will also be crucial for sustaining balanced and inclusive growth, ensuring that public resources generate measurable social and economic returns.

Comparative evidence from Japan and OECD economies suggests that macroeconomic stability is best achieved when fiscal discipline, transparent tax administration, and monetary credibility are pursued jointly [15,16]. In these advanced systems, clear policy rules, credible institutions, and evidence-based decision-making minimize uncertainty and enhance investor confidence. Uzbekistan's gradual alignment with these principles reflects a maturing policy framework that supports inclusive and resilient economic development. Continued commitment to institutional strengthening, evidence-based policymaking, and the integration of global best practices will determine how effectively Uzbekistan consolidates its gains and progresses toward the strategic objectives set under the "Uzbekistan - 2030" vision.

Ultimately, the experience of 2020-2024 demonstrates that coordinated, transparent, and adaptive policymaking-anchored in fiscal prudence, monetary credibility, and open trade-remains the most reliable path toward durable macroeconomic stability and long-term prosperity.

5. CONCLUSION

Uzbekistan's experience between 2020 and 2024 demonstrates that balanced fiscal, monetary, and customs-tariff coordination can significantly strengthen national economic stability. Fiscal reforms expanded the tax base and optimized rates; monetary policy effectively curbed inflation; and tariff liberalization secured food and trade stability.

To maintain this trajectory, future policies should focus on:

Further digitalization of tax administration;

Strengthening inflation-targeting frameworks;

Enhancing customs efficiency through data integration; and

Linking fiscal incentives to employment and environmental outcomes.

These strategies will help Uzbekistan sustain macroeconomic resilience and achieve the development goals outlined in the "Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy.

References

1. IMF. Fiscal Monitor: Strengthening the Credibility of Public Finances. Washington, DC; 2021.
2. World Bank. Uzbekistan Economic Update. Washington, DC; 2023.
3. Republic of Uzbekistan. New Tax Code. Tashkent; 2020.
4. Ministry of Finance. Budget Policy Report 2024. Tashkent; 2024.
5. Central Bank of Uzbekistan. Monetary Policy Review. Tashkent; 2024.
6. OECD. Trade Policy Reviews 2023. Paris: OECD Publishing; 2023.
7. WTO. Trade Facilitation and Customs Reform: Case of Uzbekistan. Geneva; 2024.
8. State Statistics Committee. Budget Indicators of Uzbekistan (2020-2024). Tashkent; 2025.
9. Malikov T. Tax burden dynamics and enterprise efficiency. Fiscal Studies Uzbekistan. 2024;9(2):33-47.
10. Central Bank of Uzbekistan. Inflation Report 2024. Tashkent; 2024.
11. IMF. Article IV Consultation Report: Uzbekistan. Washington, DC; 2024.
12. Microcreditbank. Annual Development Report 2024. Tashkent; 2024.
13. FAO. Global Food Outlook. Rome; 2023.
14. Tanzi V, Zee H. Tax Policy for Emerging Economies. IMF Working Paper; 2001.
15. Maekawa H. Monetary Stability and Growth: Lessons from Japan. Tokyo: BOJ Publications; 1982.
16. OECD. Public Finance in the 21st Century. Paris: OECD; 2022.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 10

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>